

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D2.4.2

Comparative Analysis of Long-Term Data Preservation Surveys: NFDI4Earth M2.4, EOSC EDEN, and FIDELIS

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Executive summary

As long-term preservation becomes a priority in research data management, it is crucial to assess how institutions define, implement, and support these practices. This report synthesises findings from three recent surveys: NFDI4Earth M2.4 (Germany), EOSC EDEN, and FIDELIS (both European initiatives), which collectively explore infrastructure, policy, and operational maturity related to long-term preservation of digital data. Rather than repeating efforts, our measure strategically opted not to launch a second national survey, instead leveraging overlapping insights from the EOSC initiatives. The consolidated analysis reveals common strengths in policy ambition but widespread operational fragmentation and training gaps. This document highlights shared challenges, illustrates complementary findings, and suggests integration pathways for national-level strategies, especially in aligning terminology, capacity building, and certification standards.

Abbreviations

DOI – Digital Object Identifier

EDEN – Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level (EOSC project)

EOSC – European Open Science Cloud

ESS – Earth System Sciences

FAIR – FAIR Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

FIDELIS – Federated Infrastructures for Digital Long-term Archiving and Preservation

LTA – Long-Term Archiving

LTS – Long-Term Storage

M2.4 – NFDI4Earth Measure 2.4 Data in Long-Term Storage

NFDI – National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur)

NFDI4Earth – NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences (NFDI Konsortium Erdsystemforschung)

OAIS – Open Archival Information System

ORCID – Open Researcher and Contributor ID

PID – Persistent Identifier

ROR – Research Organization Registry

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1 Introduction

This report evaluates three surveys conducted across different organisational and geographical scopes, all focused on long-term preservation of digital data. The German NFDI4Earth (<https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>) Measure 2.4 (M2.4) survey (2023) is compared against the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS surveys (2025; shared umbrella project page at <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>). The objective is to analyse shared thematic coverage, highlight complementary findings, and justify the decision not to initiate a second NFDI4Earth survey.

Long-term preservation of research data has become a key concern for research infrastructure initiatives, particularly those aiming to ensure scientific reproducibility, interdisciplinary accessibility, and compliance with funder mandates. Each of the three surveys discussed here contributes distinct yet overlapping insights into the current state of infrastructure, legal and organisational frameworks, and technical standards needed for reliable long-term digital preservation. Together, they provide a multi-layered view of the preservation landscape from both national (Germany-focused) and pan-European perspectives.

2 Background and Strategic Context

NFDI4Earth's Measure 2.4 focuses on improving long-term preservation of research data for the Earth System Sciences (ESS) community in Germany. The first M2.4 survey (D2.4.1) was conducted in early 2023 to understand existing infrastructure, data practices, and institutional readiness (Paul-Stüve, Schürmann, & Valena, 2024).

Shortly afterward, the EOSC-funded (European Open Science Cloud, <https://eosc.eu/>) projects EDEN and FIDELIS launched their own surveys. The EDEN survey targeted the identification, appraisal, and selection of research data for preservation (Molloy et al., 2025a, 2025b; Benauer, 2025). The FIDELIS surveys addressed repository practices, preservation service levels, legal frameworks, trust-building mechanisms, and training needs (Jouneau et al., 2025; Conzett et al., 2025). Because these surveys addressed nearly identical content areas as M2.4, our M2.4 team decided that a second national survey would not offer additional value.

3 Survey Overviews and Methodological Profiles

- **NFDI4Earth M2.4 Survey (2023)**

- 106 total participants (54 full completions)
- 36 questions focused on ESS community practices in Germany
- Distinction between long-term storage (LTS; ~10 years) and long-term archiving (LTA; potentially indefinitely)
- Data collected anonymously, structured around workflow, infrastructure, and metadata standards

- **EOSC EDEN Survey (2025)**

- 250 respondents from a diverse range of European and international institutions
- Open to European and global stakeholders (data professionals, repositories, libraries, etc.)
- Focused on appraisal, selection, ingest processes, and framework use
- Identified patterns of practice across disciplines and sectors

- **FIDELIS Surveys (2025)**

- 159 responses from repositories across 27 countries
- Focused on levels of preservation care, repository maturity, FAIR principles, legal form, and training support
- Included metadata on repository size, affiliation (e.g., ERICs, national infrastructure), and certification levels

4 Comparative Thematic Analysis

4.1 Terminology and Scope

- **NFDI4Earth** clearly distinguishes between LTS and LTA in technical and policy terms, enabling structured national discussions about minimum preservation timeframes and institutional responsibility.
- **EDEN** found that 52% of respondents (n=130) reported an agreed or working definition of 'long-term' in their organisation, while 48% reported having no such definition.
- **FIDELIS** used preservation levels to articulate the degree of service provided, avoiding time-based definitions but capturing institutional intention and operational complexity.

4.2 Policy and Legal Frameworks

- **NFDI4Earth** reported that many ESS institutions lacked formalised policies or roles for long-term data preservation; legal concerns such as data ownership or liability were often unclear or undocumented.
- **EDEN** emphasised policy gaps at the operational level, with institutions reporting uncertainty over who is responsible for data appraisal, and under what internal or external guidance frameworks.
- **FIDELIS** found repository legal forms varied widely, from informal academic collaborations to formal national archives. The presence of legal structures was correlated with funding security and preservation maturity.

4.3 Infrastructure and Ingest Processes

- **NFDI4Earth** showed that many institutions operate fragmented or non-integrated infrastructure. Technical challenges included inconsistent metadata schemas, insufficient use of persistent identifiers, and varying degrees of automation in ingest workflows.
- **EDEN** highlighted self-deposit by researchers as the most common ingest pathway. Few institutions reported active curation or automation at scale, and only a minority used third-party curation roles or selection frameworks.
- **FIDELIS** assessed repository maturity using infrastructure indicators like PID support (DOI, ROR, ORCID), use of standards (e.g., OAIS, CCSDS 650.0-M-3, see <https://ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m3.pdf>), and alignment with FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

4.4 Preservation Strategies and Curation Levels

- **NFDI4Earth** asked respondents to describe their current practices in file formats, metadata quality, and medium-term vs. long-term preservation strategies. Institutions reported concerns over obsolescence and lack of storage redundancy.
- **EDEN** reported that around 85% of respondents perform some form of quality assessment at ingest (most commonly checks of descriptive metadata and administrative metadata), but only 28% reported regularly re-assessing the quality of preserved objects later in the preservation period, suggesting that ongoing monitoring is less established than initial ingest controls. This critically low re-assessment rate underscores the need for clear operational guidance; the Guidelines developed under D2.4.5 (Schürmann & Valena, 2026) directly address this gap by providing structured recommendations for continuous quality monitoring throughout the preservation lifecycle.
- **FIDELIS** organised curation practices into four levels:

- *As deposited*: Little or no change from submission
- *Deposit compliance*: Technical checks against repository requirements
- *Initial curation*: Metadata enhancements and minor adjustments
- *Active preservation*: Long-term transformations and preservation planning with disciplinary stakeholders

4.5 Training, Support, and Organisational Capacity

- **NFDI4Earth** participants emphasised a lack of staff time and expertise in long-term preservation. Many institutions rely on one or two key personnel with insufficient time to implement systemic practices.
- **EDEN** showed that institutional staff often lacked formal training in appraisal and relied on ad hoc decision-making. Several respondents called for harmonised guidance documents or inter-institutional knowledge exchanges.
- **FIDELIS** highlighted the demand for coordinated training strategies at both national and EU levels, and mapped affiliations with capacity-building networks (e.g., EOSC Association, CoreTrustSeal, see <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>).

5 Synthesising EOSC and NFDI4Earth Surveys

The original NFDI4Earth project plan (Bernard et al., 2021) included a second survey; however, after internal evaluation, our team concluded that repeating the survey would not be beneficial. This decision was based on several considerations. First, there was significant thematic overlap with the more recent and methodologically comprehensive EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS surveys. Second, the close timing of these surveys, conducted between 2023 and 2025, enabled meaningful comparison with NFDI4Earth's results while ensuring the respondent communities remained relevant and engaged. The two-year gap between the NFDI4Earth survey (2023) and the EOSC surveys (2025) is considered acceptable, as no major structural changes, new national initiatives, or policy shifts are known to have substantially altered the long-term preservation landscape within the NFDI4Earth community during this period. Third, the EOSC surveys offered broad accessibility and were designed to capture diverse perspectives, including those from German institutions, making their results applicable and informative for the national context.

Instead, our team chose to build the deliverable D2.4.2 upon a comparative analysis, using EOSC findings to enrich NFDI4Earth's national guidance, rather than duplicate efforts with another survey.

6 Summary and Outlook

This comparative analysis confirms that the NFDI4Earth M2.4, EOSC EDEN, and FIDELIS surveys collectively capture the key challenges and emerging solutions in long-term data preservation across institutional and national contexts. Despite differences in scale and audience, the surveys consistently identify similar areas of concern: lack of formal preservation policies, insufficient staff training, fragmentation of technical infrastructure, and ambiguity in role definitions.

These findings present actionable opportunities for NFDI4Earth and similar initiatives. First, national guidelines can explicitly draw from EOSC-level results to create preservation standards that are both ambitious and achievable. A harmonised terminology around long-term digital preservation, refined through this comparative insight, should be disseminated across German institutions to promote clarity and consistency.

Second, capacity-building efforts could focus on developing modular training programmes tailored to the maturity levels of different repositories. These could be delivered through webinars, certification schemes, or integration into existing institutional curricula. Partnerships with European initiatives like CoreTrustSeal could ensure these programmes align with international best practices.

Third, findings on infrastructure and ingest workflows suggest the need for investment in interoperable systems and clearer role delegation models. Institutions should be encouraged to pilot shared infrastructure models or repository consortia, reducing redundancy while improving sustainability and compliance.

Fourth, it is recommended to investigate whether the FIDELIS Curation Levels could serve as a gold standard for NFDI4Earth. With their four-tier framework ranging from “as deposited” to “active preservation,” the FIDELIS levels offer a well-validated and internationally aligned model for describing and communicating preservation service commitments. Evaluating their applicability to the German ESS community could be formulated as a concrete work assignment for future NFDI task forces.

Finally, the comparative framework developed here could serve as a basic template for future monitoring efforts. By establishing a structured assessment method, national and EU bodies can track progress over time and ensure that long-term preservation remains a visible and strategic component of open science infrastructure.

The following table (see Tab. 1) synthesises the most urgent findings emerging from all three surveys, serving as a structured re-assessment of priorities for the NFDI4Earth community.

Table 1: Priority Issues Identified Across Surveys (Re-Assessment Overview)

Priority Issue	Surveys Flagging	Urgency / Recommended Action
Low re-assessment rate (only 28% regularly monitor preserved objects)	EDEN, NFDI4Earth	High — Address via Guidelines
Lack of formal preservation policies and unclear roles	All three surveys	High — Develop national guidance frameworks; engage IG LTA
Insufficient staff training and over-reliance on key personnel	All three surveys	High — Modular training programmes; certification partnerships (e.g., CoreTrustSeal)
Fragmented and non-interoperable infrastructure	NFDI4Earth, FIDELIS	Medium — Pilot shared infrastructure models and repository consortia
Terminology inconsistency (no agreed definition of “long-term” in 48% of institutions)	EDEN, NFDI4Earth	Medium — Harmonise terminology across institutions via national guidelines

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